

RS-Net: Neural Network-enhanced Receivers for MIMO Rate Splitting Multiple Access

Dheeraj Raja Kumar, Carles Antón-Haro and Xavier Mestre
Centre Tecnologic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC/iCERCA)
Parc Mediterrani de la Tecnologia, Av Carl Friedrich Gauss 7
Castelldefels, Barcelona
{dheeraj.raja.kumar, carles.anton, xavier.mestre}@cttc.es

Abstract—Non-orthogonal multiple access techniques are a promising approach, which in combination with multi-antenna processing can achieve substantial gains in terms of rate and transmission quality. However, the use of these techniques typically involves sequential interference cancellation (SIC) at the receiver, which is far from robust to system model imperfections such as channel estimation errors. In order to achieve a higher degree of robustness to these imperfections, this paper studies the use of data-driven algorithms in order to replace some of the blocks of a conventional multi-antenna SIC receiver. The focus here is on Rate Splitting Multiple Access (RSMA) architectures that are subject to imperfect channel state information at both the transmitter and the receiver. The study illustrates that neural network based techniques can be very helpful in order to guarantee a higher degree of robustness of the transceiver, provided that they are conveniently fed and trained with the suitable information. The emphasis is on architectures that do not need to be retrained at each channel realization, so that computational complexity is comparable to conventional receivers.

I. INTRODUCTION

MIMO technology makes it possible to spatially multiplex a high number of users. As a result, the spectral and energy efficiency of communication systems can be substantially improved [1]. In contrast with traditional orthogonal multiple access (OMA) schemes where users are scheduled in orthogonal dimensions (time, frequency), non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA) allows to superpose users in the same time frequency resource. This can be achieved by employing superposition coding at the transmitters and sequential interference cancellation (SIC) at the receivers.

Rate Splitting Multiple Access (RSMA), also a non-orthogonal transmission scheme, has been shown to outperform NOMA [2], [3] in MIMO settings both in terms of sum multiplexing gain and efficient use of SIC. The simplest and most practical RSMA scheme is proposed RS, which is the basic building block of almost all existing RSMA schemes. It involves decoding of common message symbols (common to all the users) followed by SIC and decoding of individual private messages. In this manner, RS scheme partially decodes the multi-user interference, while partially treating it as noise.

Both NOMA and RSMA strongly rely on SIC at the receiver, which is the most critical point in practical imple-

mentations. The presence of model imperfections (channel estimation errors, synchronization issues, RF imperfections, etc.) in the SIC operations lead to error propagation which significantly degrades the symbol detection performance. Deep Learning (DL) approaches are particularly suitable for overcoming such limitations. For example, the work in [4] considers an uplink MIMO-NOMA scenario where deep neural networks (DNNs) are employed in a successive manner to decode all the user symbols. Each SIC step is replaced with a DNN, which results in the receiver requiring as many DNN blocks as the number of users in the system. On the other hand, [5] focuses on downlink NOMA and proposes the use of DNNs at both transmitter and receivers to jointly optimize the precoding and symbol detection. Each SIC step consists of two DNNs (one for decoding the symbol of preceding user, and the second to perform the actual SIC operation) making this approach computationally intensive. The above two approaches require the neural networks to be trained for *each* channel realization since the channel coefficients are not explicitly estimated. This is also the case of [6], which considers the use of DNNs for performing both the SIC operation and symbol detection at the receivers in NOMA downlink. It outperforms the conventional SIC receiver with full CSIR, however channel conditions are assumed static during both the training and testing periods of the DNNs.

Focusing more on the RSMA setting, [7] proposes the use of DNNs to replace specific blocks in the receiver to efficiently decode common and private message symbols in the downlink. The issue of CSIR availability is addressed by comparing the symbol detection against conventional SIC receiver with imperfect CSIR. The importance of the system training overhead is highlighted in this work by defining a *training sub-block* which consists of dedicated training symbols followed by data symbols to be predicted. Having considered block fading channels, the proposed approach shows better performance than SIC receivers with imperfect CSIR.

In this paper, we propose the use of DNNs to carry out three independent tasks: channel estimation, symbol detection, and SIC operation in a MIMO-RSMA scenario. The resulting architecture will be referred to in the sequel as RS-Net. By incorporating an explicit channel estimation block, the DNNs do not need to be re-trained for each channel realization, as it was the case in [4], [5]. For a given system setting, they

This work was supported by grants PID2021-128373OB-I00, PRE2019-089309 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by “ERDF A way of making Europe”, and 2021 SGR00772 from Generalitat de Catalunya.

Fig. 1. One-layer RS model with K users. The common stream W_c is intended for all users, whereas private streams are individual to each user.

are trained offline once, thus eliminating the need for training symbols during pilot transmission of each frame, resulting in a much lower training overhead compared to [7]. Unlike [5], in our scheme the SIC and symbol detection steps are performed by a *single* NN, allowing to reduce its computational complexity. Moreover, we propose an enhanced architecture, RS-Net+, whereby soft estimates of the private message are also used for the decoding of the common message to boost its performance. To the best of our knowledge, this scheme has not been proposed before. Finally, we propose a transmit precoding strategy to avoid cross-interference between private streams and analyze the impact of imperfect CSIT on the performance of RS-Net.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

Consider the downlink of a multi-user MIMO system where one Base Station (BS) equipped with N_T transmit antennas serves K users with N_R antennas each. In proposed RS, the message W_k intended for the k -th user is split at the transmitter into two sub-messages namely, one common sub-message $W_{c,k}$ and one private sub-message $W_{p,k}$. The common sub-messages of all users $W_{c,1}, \dots, W_{c,K}$ are combined into one common message W_c and encoded into a common stream s_c using a codebook shared by all users. The entire common message W_c has to be decoded by all users, yet only the corresponding sub-message $W_{c,k}$ is of interest to the k -th user. The private sub-messages of all users $W_{p,1}, \dots, W_{p,K}$ are independently encoded into private streams s_1, \dots, s_K , which are decoded by the corresponding users only. Therefore, $K+1$ streams, i.e. $\mathbf{s} = [s_c, s_1, \dots, s_K]^T \in \mathbb{C}^{(K+1) \times 1}$ are created from the K messages W_1, \dots, W_K . Figure 1 illustrates a typical scenario of MIMO 1-layer RSMA system.

The streams are linearly transformed via multiplication with the precoding matrix $\mathbf{P} = [\mathbf{p}_c, \mathbf{p}_1, \dots, \mathbf{p}_K]$ where $\mathbf{p}_c, \mathbf{p}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{N_T \times 1}, k = 1, \dots, K$ are the unit-norm beamforming vectors. The transmit signal thus reads

$$\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{P}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{s} = \alpha_c \mathbf{p}_c s_c + \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_k \mathbf{p}_k s_k \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{A} is a diagonal matrix containing the values $\alpha_c, \alpha_k \in [0, 1]$ for $k = 1, \dots, K$, which are the coefficients that control the amount of power that is allocated to the

common and private message streams. They are assumed to be normalized, such that $\alpha_c^2 + \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_k^2 = 1$. The received signal at k -th user is thus given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{y}_k &= \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{P} \mathbf{A} \mathbf{s} + \mathbf{n}_k \\ &= \mathbf{H}_k \alpha_c \mathbf{p}_c s_c + \mathbf{H}_k \alpha_k \mathbf{p}_k s_k + \sum_{j \neq k} \mathbf{H}_k \alpha_j \mathbf{p}_j s_j + \mathbf{n}_k \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{H}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{N_R \times N_T}$ is the channel matrix of the k -th user and \mathbf{n}_k denotes i.i.d. Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) with zero mean and variance σ^2 . We assume an under-loaded scenario where $N_T \geq K N_R$. At the receiver, each user first decodes the common stream s_c into W_c by treating the interference from all private streams as noise. Using Successive Interference Cancellation (SIC), W_c is then re-encoded, precoded, and subtracted from the received signal such that user- k decodes its private stream s_k into $W_{p,k}$ by treating the remaining interference from the other private streams as noise. Finally, the k -th user reconstructs the original message by extracting $W_{c,k}$ from W_c , and combining $W_{c,k}$ with $W_{p,k}$ into W_k .

A. Design of the precoding matrix

With respect to the design of the precoding matrix \mathbf{P} , the first column of this matrix corresponds to the precoder of the common stream \mathbf{p}_c , which must be built such that the message is received by all the users in the system. To achieve this, we select \mathbf{p}_c as the principal eigenvector (i.e., eigenvector associated to the largest eigenvalue) of the matrix $\sum_{k=1}^K \mathbf{H}_k^H \mathbf{H}_k$. This guarantees that the transmitted power is maximized towards all the directions where users are present, without per-user priorities. Regarding the precoder vectors associated to the private streams, we build them so that they are completely orthogonal to one another while maximizing the received power towards the user of interest. To formulate this, consider the following $(K-1)N_R \times N_T$ channel matrix

$$\mathbf{H}_{(k)} = [\mathbf{H}_1^T, \dots, \mathbf{H}_{k-1}^T, \mathbf{H}_{k+1}^T, \dots, \mathbf{H}_K^T]^T$$

which is formed by stacking the channel matrices of all users *except for the k -th user* on top of one another. Let \mathbf{Q}_k denote the unique $N_T \times N_T - (K-1)N_R$ matrix of orthogonal columns such that

$$\mathbf{H}_{(k)} \mathbf{Q}_k = \mathbf{0}.$$

In other words, the columns of \mathbf{Q}_k span the orthogonal complement (of rank $N_T - (K-1)N_R$) to the subspace spanned by the rows of $\mathbf{H}_{(k)}$. It is to be noted that this guarantees $\mathbf{H}_j \mathbf{Q}_k = \mathbf{0}$ for all $j \neq k$. The k -th precoding vector \mathbf{p}_k is therefore built as $\mathbf{p}_k = \mathbf{Q}_k \mathbf{w}_k$, where \mathbf{w}_k is the principal eigenvector of the matrix $\mathbf{Q}_k^H \mathbf{H}_k^H \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{Q}_k$.

In this work, we also consider the case of imperfect precoders resulting from the use of noisy channel estimates $\hat{\mathbf{H}}_k$ (instead of \mathbf{H}_k) in the preceding expressions. To model this, we let $\hat{\mathbf{H}}_k = \mathbf{H}_k + \mathbf{N}_k$, where $\mathbf{N}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{N_R \times N_T}$ represents the zero-mean AWGN of variance β^2 . With imperfect precoders, the orthogonality of the private messages is not preserved. In the computer simulation results, we analyze how this impacts the performance of NN-based and conventional receivers.

B. Optimum and Conventional RSMA Receivers

As benchmarks, we adopt (i) the Maximum Likelihood (ML) receiver, which is optimal yet computationally intensive; and (ii) two sub-optimal receivers: the Linear Minimum Mean Square Error (LMMSE) and Successive Interference Cancellation (SIC) receivers.

For the ML receiver, all the common and private message pairs $(\widehat{W}_c, \widehat{W}_j)$ for all j are computed by the minimum distance estimation rule as

$$\operatorname{argmin}_{W_c, W_1, \dots, W_K} \|\mathbf{y}_k - \mathbf{H}_k \alpha_c \mathbf{p}_c \phi_c(W_c) - \sum_j \mathbf{H}_k \alpha_j \mathbf{p}_j \phi_j(W_j)\|^2$$

where $\phi_c(\cdot), \phi_j(\cdot)$ represent the encoding and modulating functionality of the common and private messages of j -th user.

Alternatively, when the receiver is equipped with multiple antennas, a conventional LMMSE receiver could be used to (i) *jointly* estimate the common and private messages; and (ii) mitigate the interference caused by the other private messages (owing to the additional spatial dimension). In this case, assuming that the transmitted symbols are zero-mean with unit power, the estimates read

$$[\hat{s}_c^{(\text{LMMSE})}, \hat{s}_k^{(\text{LMMSE})}]^T = \mathbf{H}_k^{(\text{eq})H} \mathbf{C}_k^{-1} \mathbf{y}_k$$

where $\mathbf{H}_k^{(\text{eq})}$ is the $N_R \times 2$ *equivalent* channel given by the product of the *actual* channel matrix and the precoding vectors for the common and private messages:

$$\mathbf{H}_k^{(\text{eq})} = \mathbf{H}_k [\alpha_c \mathbf{p}_c, \alpha_k \mathbf{p}_k] \quad (3)$$

and \mathbf{C}_k is the covariance matrix of the signal at the k -th user

$$\mathbf{C}_k = \alpha_c^2 \mathbf{H}_j \mathbf{p}_c \mathbf{p}_c^H \mathbf{H}_j^H + \sum_{j=1}^K \alpha_j^2 \mathbf{H}_j \mathbf{p}_j \mathbf{p}_j^H \mathbf{H}_j^H + \sigma^2 \mathbf{I}_{N_R}.$$

SIC turns out to be an easier alternative. First, it estimates the common symbol using an LMMSE receiver:

$$\hat{s}_c^{(\text{SIC})} = \alpha_c \mathbf{p}_c^H \mathbf{H}_k^H \mathbf{C}_k^{-1} \mathbf{y}_k.$$

After performing a hard decision on $\hat{s}_c^{(\text{SIC})}$ and subtracting (from the received signal) the regenerated input signal corresponding to the common part, an estimate of the private symbol can be obtained by using the LMMSE receiver:

$$\hat{s}_k^{(\text{SIC})} = \alpha_k \mathbf{p}_k^H \mathbf{H}_k^H \tilde{\mathbf{C}}_k^{-1} \mathbf{y}_k.$$

where the corresponding covariance matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{C}}_k$ now reads

$$\tilde{\mathbf{C}}_k = \sum_{j=1}^K \alpha_j^2 \mathbf{H}_j \mathbf{p}_j \mathbf{p}_j^H \mathbf{H}_j^H + \sigma^2 \mathbf{I}_{N_R}.$$

III. RS-NET: AN NN-ENHANCED RSMA RECEIVER

In this section, we leverage the traditional SIC architecture for the receiver and replace (i) the conventional channel estimation block; (ii) data detection block for the common stream; and (iii) the signal re-construction, pre-coding and subtraction blocks needed to detect the private stream by their NN counterparts. The resulting scheme is depicted in Figure 2. In the sequel, it is referred to as *RS-Net*.

Fig. 2. Proposed RS-Net receiver architecture for decoding the common (s_c) and private (s_k) streams of user- k .

Fig. 3. 1D-CNN for channel estimation.

A. Channel estimation via 1D-CNNs

Channel estimation can be modelled as a supervised learning regression problem. To address it, we resort to *shallow* 1D-CNNs (Convolutional Neural Networks) given its superior performance [8].

Specifically, channel estimation can be cast into a multi-output regression task where:

- The input of the 1D-CNN (see Figure 3) is given by $\tilde{\mathbf{Y}} = \text{vec}[\text{Re}(\mathbf{Y}_k) \otimes [1, 0] + \text{Im}(\mathbf{Y}_k) \otimes [0, 1]]$ where $\mathbf{Y}_k = [\mathbf{y}_1, \dots, \mathbf{y}_{N_P}] \in \mathbb{C}^{N_R \times N_P}$ are the received signals of user- k on transmitting N_P pilot symbols. The vector is then reshaped to size $N_R \times 2N_P$
- The output is the effective channel vector $\text{vec}[\text{Re}(\mathbf{H}_k^{(\text{eq})}) \otimes [1, 0] + \text{Im}(\mathbf{H}_k^{(\text{eq})}) \otimes [0, 1]]$ where $\mathbf{H}_k^{(\text{eq})} = \mathbf{H}_k [\alpha_c \mathbf{p}_c, \alpha_k \mathbf{p}_k]$ is the effective channel matrix defined in (3).

In 1D-Convolutional Neural Networks (1D-CNN), the trainable weights are arranged in 2-D kernels for convolution operations. However, these kernels slide in *one* direction only (e.g., along the time axis) to produce feature maps. This scheme is prominently used for processing time-series data. The pilot symbols sent from the transmitter can be viewed as a time-series, making the application of 1D-CNN suitable for channel estimation. As shown in Figure 3, there are as many feature maps as the number of kernels N_k in the convolutional layer. The feature maps are then flattened and connected to the output layer. This 1D-CNN is said to be shallow since it comprises a single convolutional layer. The use of 1D-CNN for channel estimation was thoroughly investigated in our previous research. For more details, please, refer to [8].

B. Symbol detection via DNNs

Data (symbol) detection can be modeled as a supervised learning classification problem and be solved via feed-forward DNNs (Deep Neural Networks). In particular, it can be cast into a multi-class classification task where:

- The input of the DNN for the detection of the *common* message symbol is given by (i) the received signal \mathbf{y}_k ; and (ii) the actual (or estimated) equivalent channel matrix $\mathbf{H}_k^{(\text{eq})}$ re-shaped into a row vector $\mathbf{t} = [\mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{H}_k^{(\text{eq})}]$. In addition to these inputs, the DNN for the detection of the *private* symbols also takes in the estimated common symbol obtained by the previous neural network (see Figure 2). The *Map* block transforms the discrete output (an index, see next bullet) of the NN in a modulated symbol suitable for transmission.
- The output is an index b to the set of transmitted symbols. For a QPSK signal in each stream, we have $b \in [1, \dots, B]$ with $B = 4^{N_T}$, denoting a set of cardinality 4^{N_T} .

Feed-forward Deep Neural Networks includes the so-called Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP). The L -layer MLP consists of: (i) one input layer with $2N_R$ elements (the real and imaginary parts of the received signal) and the estimated effective common channel coefficients $\mathbf{H}_k^{(\text{eq})}$ from the previous 1D-CNN; (ii) one output layer with B neurons; and (iii) $L - 2$ hidden layers with $N_l; l = 2, \dots, L - 1$ neurons each. This MLP defines a mapping $f(\mathbf{t}, \Phi) : \mathbb{R}^{2N_R(1+N_T)} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^B$ of an input vector \mathbf{t} onto an output vector \mathbf{r}_L through L iterative processing steps $\mathbf{r}_l = f_l(\mathbf{r}_{l-1}; \phi_l); l = 1 \dots L$ where $f_l(\mathbf{r}_{l-1}, \phi_l) : \mathbb{R}^{N_{l-1}} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{N_l}$ is the mapping associated to the l -th layer. This mapping depends on the output from the previous layer and on the parameter set of the said layer, ϕ_l , with $\Phi = [\phi_1, \dots, \phi_L]$ denoting the set of all parameters in the model. The l -th layer is said to be *dense* if $f_l(\mathbf{r}_{l-1}; \phi_l)$ is of the form $f_l(\mathbf{r}_{l-1}; \phi_l) = \sigma(\mathbf{G}_l \mathbf{r}_{l-1} + \mathbf{u}_l)$ with $\mathbf{G}_l \in \mathbb{R}^{N_l \times N_{l-1}}$ and $\mathbf{u}_l \in \mathbb{R}^{N_l}$ denoting matrix of weights and bias vector, while $\sigma(\cdot)$ is a (typically non-linear) activation function. In this work, Rectified Linear Units (ReLU) are used as activation functions in all hidden layers. The output layer has the Softmax activation function, to compute the probability for each set of transmit symbols. Further, each dense layer is followed by a batch normalization and dropout layer to avoid overfitting to the training dataset.

In the training phase, the parameter set in each layer, i.e., $\phi_l = [\mathbf{G}_l, \mathbf{u}_l]$, is adjusted via the stochastic adaptive gradient descent algorithm (Adagrad, [9]) and backpropagation [10]. The goal is to minimize the categorical cross entropy, thereby maximizing classification accuracy (i.e., minimize SER).

C. Considerations on training

RS-Net does not require re-training of the neural networks for each channel realization or on a frame-by-frame basis. The various neural networks are trained offline and can be used for channel estimation or symbol detection as long as the system scenario i.e., number of transmit antennas, users, and channel statistics remain unchanged.

The training dataset for *channel estimation* comprises a total of M examples of received signals $\tilde{\mathbf{Y}}^{(m)}, m = 1, \dots, M$ as input features, and the corresponding equivalent (vector) channel as labels, as per the definition in Section III-A. For the symbol detection blocks, the input features are the received signal and the equivalent channel, whereas the output is the corresponding common (or private) symbol. The creation of training set comprises the following steps:

- 1) Generation of the received signal for a total of M realizations of the communication scenario. For each realization of the channel, N_P pilot symbols and noise vectors are generated, followed by N_D data symbols.
- 2) Letting the label of each pilot symbol block be the actual effective channel response. The labels for the symbol detection blocks are set to be the associated common and private symbol for each example.

D. RS-Net+ : an advanced architecture

For *multi-antenna* users, we propose an advanced version of the architecture that takes advantage of the additional spatial degrees of freedom. Here, along with $\mathbf{H}_k^{(\text{eq})}$ the common message detection block takes an additional input: a soft-estimate of the *intended* private message symbol (see dashed box in Figure 2). The intuition behind providing a soft estimate of the private message symbol *and* the corresponding estimate of the private channel (which is part of $\mathbf{H}_k^{(\text{eq})}$) is to facilitate the trained common message detection to implicitly reconstruct and subtract the contribution of the private message to the received signal. In this manner, the estimate of the transmitted common symbol can be improved.

The soft estimate of the private symbol can be independently computed from the received signal and effective channel matrix of the k -th user as (the derivation is omitted for brevity):

$$\hat{\mathbf{s}}_{\text{p-soft},k} = \frac{(\mathbf{H}_k \alpha_k \mathbf{p}_k)^H \mathbf{P}_c^\perp \mathbf{y}_k}{\sigma^2 + (\mathbf{H}_k \alpha_k \mathbf{p}_k)^H \mathbf{P}_c^\perp \mathbf{h}_k \alpha_k \mathbf{p}_k} \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{P}_c^\perp is the orthogonal projection matrix (which is only defined for $N_R > 1$) onto the null space of the equivalent common message channel vector $\mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{p}_c$, that is

$$\mathbf{P}_c^\perp = \mathbf{I}_{N_R} - \frac{\mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{p}_c \mathbf{p}_c^H \mathbf{H}_k^H}{\mathbf{p}_c^H \mathbf{H}_k^H \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{p}_c}$$

The above soft estimate can be seen as an LMMSE estimator of the private intended symbol when the common symbol is estimated according to the maximum-likelihood principle.

IV. COMPUTER SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, we assess the performance of the proposed *RS-Net* scheme in a scenario with $K=2$ *single-* and *multi-antenna* users, and $N_T = \{3, 6\}$ transmit antennas, respectively. A different *RS-Net* scheme is fit for each SNR in the range of interest. For the implementation, training, and evaluation of the proposed scheme, we use Keras on a TensorFlow backend. For the stochastic adaptive gradient descent algorithm (Adagrad), the learning rate is set to 0.01, and a batch size of 512 samples is used for the computation

Fig. 4. Symbol error rate for the maximum-likelihood detector vs. power allocation α_k in the private streams ($N_T = 3$, $N_R = 1$, $K = 2$).

of gradient of the neural networks. Out of the $M = 10^4$ examples in the generated dataset, 20% are used for validation purposes. All the neural networks are trained for 50 epochs, to reach convergence. The hyperparameters are optimized via grid search. As for precoder imperfection, we consider cases with noise variance $\beta^2 = 0$ (perfect precoding, orthogonal private messages), and $\beta^2 = 0.1$ (imperfect, non-orthogonal).

A. Optimum Power Allocation

Firstly, we attempt to determine the optimum power allocation among the common and private message streams. As explained in Section II, the power allocation coefficients (α_c, α_k) of the common and private message streams are governed by $\alpha_c^2 + \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_k^2 = 1$. Given the symmetry of the scenario, we will restrict ourselves to the case of identical power allocation to all private messages (i.e., $\alpha_k = \alpha$ for all k). Specifically, we will adopt the values that minimize the symbol error rate (SER) for the optimal maximum-likelihood receiver for the proposed RS-Net scheme and all the conventional receivers (LMMSE, SIC) in Section II-B.

Figure 4 reveals that, for the single-antenna ($N_R = 1$) case the SER curves are relatively flat in the $[0.2, 0.65]$ range for all SNR values. Similar results are obtained for the multi-antenna case. Hence, we let $\alpha_k = 0.3$ for all simulation scenarios.

B. Channel Estimation

We use $N_P = 3$ pilot symbols (bare minimum required to estimate the three channel coefficients in a two-user scenario) for the estimation of the equivalent channel matrix $\mathbf{H}_k^{(\text{eq})}$. As a benchmark, we adopt a linear Least Squares (LS) channel estimator. The estimation error is given by the squared norm of the difference between the channel estimate $\hat{\mathbf{H}}_k^{(\text{eq})}$ and $\mathbf{H}_k^{(\text{eq})} = \mathbf{H}_k[\alpha_c \mathbf{p}_c, \alpha_k \mathbf{p}_k]$. The estimation error is normalized column-wise, that is, with respect to $\|\mathbf{H}_k \alpha_c \mathbf{p}_c\|^2$ and $\|\mathbf{H}_k \alpha_k \mathbf{p}_k\|^2$, respectively.

Figure 5 depicts the Normalized Mean Square Error (NMSE) as a function of the SNR for the common and private channels of user 1 (user 2 yields similar results since the scenario is symmetric). Clearly, the private channels exhibit a higher NMSE when compared to the common channel. This is attributed to the fact that private channels are allocated a small fraction of the transmit power ($\alpha_k = 0.3$). The

Fig. 5. Channel estimation error for the 1D-CNN and LS channel estimators, for *single-* (top) and *multi-*antenna users (bottom), with perfect (left) and imperfect (right) precoders. The 1D-CNN has $N_k = 64$ kernels of size $N_R \times 2$.

figure also reveals that 1D-CNN estimators for both channels consistently outperform their LS counterparts in all scenarios and for all SNRs. In the low-SNR regime of scenarios with single-antenna users, the gain is particularly large: almost one order of magnitude. Notably, the degradation associated to the use of imperfect precoders (sub-plots on the right) is marginal. For the LS estimator in particular, the reason is that inter-user interference is accurately modeled in (2) and all system parameters in the third summation (α_k, s_k) are known (unlike additive noise, which is only statistically characterized). This allows the LS scheme to effectively estimate $\mathbf{H}_k^{(\text{eq})}$ irrespectively of the equivalent channel (which also depends on the value of β^2). Interestingly, the same behaviour is observed for the 1D-CNN estimator.

C. Symbol Detection

We evaluate the SER performance of the proposed RS-Net and RS-Net+ architectures. The benchmarks are those introduced in Section II-B, namely: ML, LMMSE, and SIC receivers. The ML receiver operates with full CSI for each channel realization \mathbf{H}_k and the actual precoders used in each scenario (be it perfect or imperfect). The conventional LMMSE and SIC receivers use the channel estimates obtained by the LS channel estimator. On the contrary, RS-Net and RS-Net+ take advantage of the NN-based channel estimates which are obtained via 1D-CNNs.

Fig. 6. Symbol Error Rate for Common and Private Symbol Detection for *single-antenna* and *multi-antenna* users in RSMA settings.

In the *RS-Net* scheme, the DNNs for detecting the common and private message streams have 1 hidden layer comprising one dense layer with 256 neurons, followed by a batch normalization and a dropout layer (with probability 0.3). The training dataset comprises $M = 10^4$ examples, and in each example the payload includes $N_D = 10$ randomly-generated data symbols. Figure 6 depicts the uncoded SER vs. the signal to noise ratio (SNR) for user 1. As expected, the curve for the ML receiver turns out to be the lower bound for the SER in all cases. Besides, by comparing the top and bottom sub-plots, it can be inferred that using multiple antennas substantially improves the achievable SER performance. As expected, the curve for the LMMSE receiver is the upper bound in the multi-antenna case which is the only scenario where LMMSE can be effectively used¹. For low SNR, RS-net substantially outperforms the conventional SIC receiver. However, for large SNR values (above 30-35dB and 20dB in single- and multi-antenna scenarios, respectively), the RS-Net curves exhibit an error floor. Interestingly, such error floor vanishes and performance substantially improves when, in addition to the equivalent channel matrix, a soft estimate of the own private

¹By definition, the SIC and LMMSE receivers are identical for the common channel. Hence, both the curves overlap.

symbol is supplied to the NN-based receiver for the common stream. This indicates that the intended private message causes significant interference on the decoding of common message (especially at high SNR) which results in the above-mentioned error floor of the *RS-Net* scheme. On the contrary, intra-user interference is effectively removed by the *RS-Net+* scheme.

The performance of the *RS-Net+* scheme in *multi-antenna* settings is closer to that of the optimal receiver, this being achieved at a fraction of its computational complexity. As for the private message streams, the performance gap between *RS-Net* and *RS-Net+* is due to error propagation from the decoding of the common stream to the private stream of the user. In the case of imperfect precoders ($\beta > 0$), all the receivers exhibit some performance degradation due to inter-user interference, with *RS-Net+* consistently offering better performance than the conventional LMMSE and SIC receivers.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The performance of SIC receivers for RSMA transmissions can clearly benefit from the use of data-driven architectures. Firstly, the combination of precoder and channel substantially modifies the statistical behavior of the equivalent channel (which is no longer Gaussian), hence clear benefits can be obtained from non-linear estimators based on deep learning. Secondly, the SIC operations in conventional receivers can also be considered in order to guarantee a certain degree of robustness to the presence of interference, provided that the neural network can be fed with the suitable (properly processed) soft information. This gain in performance is achieved without the need to retrain the system at every change of the channel response, which clearly simplifies the operative and computational cost of the transceiver.

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